

Measurement of the Linewidth Enhancement Factor of a 1550-nm Injection-Locked Quantum Dash Laser

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Abstract: Injection-locking in quantum dash lasers is studied for the first time. A measurement of the linewidth enhancement factor from 1.2-8.6 is obtained by comparing the positive and negative detuning ranges of the stable locking regime.

I. INTRODUCTION

The linewidth enhancement factor, or α parameter, is a property of fundamental interest in the characterization of semiconductor lasers. Few of the experimental techniques used to measure α are simple to implement or capable of examining a wide range of operating conditions in the laser diode. In this work, the above threshold or “device” α of a quantum dash laser fabricated on an InP substrate is analyzed for the first time using the injection-locking technique. Previous work has evaluated α in quantum dot and dash lasers below threshold and established the validity of extracting α from the stable locking regime of strong-injected laser diodes.^{1,2,3} The present experiment shows that α is strongly power dependent for quantum dashes ranging from 1.2 near threshold to a value as high as 8.6 at twice threshold, but relatively constant across a wavelength span of 20 nm. Contrary to the well known fact that large α is undesirable for various applications, theoretical work has shown that the non-linear dynamics of large α lasers are dramatically simplified.^{4,5}

II. DEVICE STRUCTURE

The device investigated is MBE-grown on an n^+ -InP substrate. The dashes in a well (DWELL) active region consists of 5 layers of InAs quantum dashes embedded in compressively-strained $\text{Al}_{0.20}\text{Ga}_{0.16}\text{In}_{0.64}\text{As}$ quantum wells separated by 30-nm undoped tensile-strained $\text{Al}_{0.28}\text{Ga}_{0.22}\text{In}_{0.50}\text{As}$ spacers. A lattice-matched 105 nm layer of undoped $\text{Al}_{0.30}\text{Ga}_{0.18}\text{In}_{0.52}\text{As}$ is added on each side of the active region. The p-cladding layer is step-doped AlInAs with a thickness of 1.5 μm to reduce free carrier loss. The n-cladding layer is 500-nm thick AlInAs. The laser structure is capped with a 100-nm InGaAs layer. Four-micron wide ridge waveguide multi-mode Fabry-Perot lasers with 500 μm cleaved cavity lengths were fabricated. The slope efficiency is 0.2 W/A and the threshold is 45 mA.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A fiber-based optical injection set up, as shown in Fig. 1 was used for the experiment. The master laser is a New

Focus tunable laser with wavelengths ranging from 1530 nm to 1580 nm, with an accuracy of 4 pm. The New Focus laser is then connected to an Erbium-Doped Fiber Amplifier (EDFA), and then run through a band-pass filter to decrease the noise coming from the amplified master signal. From the filter a Variable Optical Attenuator (VOA) is connected that allows for greater control of the power coming from the master laser. Between the VOA and a polarization-maintaining (PM) circulator, a free-space polarization controller is inserted to ensure control of the injected field. Port 2 of the circulator is coupled to the slave laser via a PM lensed fiber, and port 3 is the diagnostic port. The diagnostic port has a 1x2 fiber coupler (5%/95%) in which the 5% end is connected to a power meter and the 95% is connected to an optical spectrum analyzer (OSA). This system allows for constant monitoring of the total power, as well as the slave power by simply blocking the master from going into port 1.

Figure 1: Experimental setup for measuring linewidth enhancement factor using the injection locking technique.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

When the master light is injected into the multi-mode slave, which is biased above threshold, the injected light competes with the optical gain of the slave for amplification. When the injected power is sufficiently strong and close to one of the free-running slave modes, an injection-locked state is achieved. Fig 2(a) is an optical power spectra of the coupled laser system. Here the master laser operated at 1567.39 nm and was operating at minimal detuning to that of the slave, which showed a side mode

suppression ratio (SMSR) of at least 35 dB. By blocking the beam of the master at the polarization controller we could measure the power of slave and also see the free running spectrum shown in Fig 2(b). The injected-to-slave field ratio, η , is approximately 1.0. Here we considered 35 dB SMSR to delineate the locked condition.

Figure 2: Optical spectra of the injection locked laser (top) and the free running slave (bottom) biased at 70 mA.

Using the stable locking condition, it is possible to find α using the positive and negative detuning limits. The equation used, validated under strong injection in quantum well lasers², is as follows:

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_{pos}}{\Delta\lambda_{neg}} = \sqrt{\alpha^2 + 1} \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta\lambda_{neg}$ is the difference between the master and the slave on the negative wavelength detuning side, and $\Delta\lambda_{pos}$ is the value on the positive side.

It was found that unless the modes are suppressed to below 35 dBm relative to the peak of the regenerated signal, they perturbed the injection locking stability boundary. This has the effect of pulling the injection locking detuning frequencies toward the stronger modes of the FP slave. This effect was discovered when trying to injection-lock to one of the weaker side-modes of the slave.

By varying the bias on the slave at a fixed wavelength, α was measured using the method described above as a function of the current above threshold for the free-running slave. The injected power ranged from -8 to -3 dBm. The data as displayed in Fig. 3 shows that α ranges from 1.2 to 8.6, which indicates a relatively large power dependence. The saturation in α with current is caused by the thermal rollover of the device. In contrast, while keeping the slave biased at 50 mA and adjusting the injected power into the slave from -12 to -3 dBm, α stayed relatively constant from 1.0 to 1.3.

The α measurement was conducted over a variety of wavelengths ranging from 1550 nm to 1573 nm at a 50 mA slave bias. The limitation to the examined range on the blue side came from unstable locking of the slave modes, and the limitation on the red side was limited by the band pass filter. The calculated value of α , 1.5, agreed at each of the different wavelengths measured, showing consistency in the data.

Figure 3: α vs current above threshold at 1555.57 nm.

An amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) spectra was obtained below threshold at 44 mA. The net modal gain, g , was extracted from the peak to valley ratio of the subthreshold oscillations using:

$$g = \frac{1}{L} \ln \left[\frac{1 + \sqrt{x} - 1}{r \sqrt{x} + 1} \right] \quad (2)$$

where L is cavity length and x is the peak to valley heights, and r is the facet reflectivity. Fig 4 is the resulting net modal gain of the laser. It is relatively flat over the experimental range of interest which is probably why α does not vary appreciably from 1550 to 1573 nm.

Figure 4: Net modal gain vs wavelength of the slave laser biased below threshold at 44mA.

V. CONCLUSION

This study examined the α parameter of a multi-mode quantum dash laser above threshold using the injection locking technique for the first time. The most significant outcome was that the α showed a strong power dependence varying from 1.2 to 8.6. This result shows that non-linear gain effects play an important role in the above-threshold linewidth enhancement factor in quantum dash lasers, similar to reported data for quantum dot light emitters.

References

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